

Comparative study of cytotoxic effect of Natural and chemical fungicide on onion root tip

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ABSTRACT

Fungicides are used to control plant based bacterial and fungal diseases. They can be chemical (synthetic) and natural fungicides, which may show same results but can have different side effects. For current study, we have selected 'Carbendazim' as a chemical fungicide, which is widely used to control fungal diseases in crops, vegetables and fruits by inhibiting fungal growth. It is categorized under systematic fungicide which is absorbed by plants and translocated within the tissues, protecting them from inborn and soil born infections. Turmeric, lemon grass and neem are considered under the category of natural fungicides which are extracted in water. Aim of study is to compare and evaluate the possible cytotoxic effect of selected natural and chemical fungicides. Chromosomal aberration such as metaphase with puff chromosome, chromosomal breakage, vagrant chromosomes in anaphase, micronuclei, anaphase bridge, c- mitosis are observed during studies.

Keywords: Natural fungicides, chemical fungicides, cytotoxic effect, chromosomal aberrations.

INTRODUCTION

Fungicides have been used in crop protection against different diseases, to increase agricultural production. Thus, they play important role in food production and security. However, excessive use of chemical fungicides in modern agriculture has negatively impacted the environment and living organisms. Many times, these fungicides accumulate in plants, environment and may affect health of other non-targeted organisms including humans. Cytotoxic effects of fungicides in plants including mitotic index and chromosomal aberrations are reported by researchers. Use of plant based natural pesticides is considered to be safer and environment friendly alternative of crop disease management. Apart from this benefit it is important to check and compare the negative effect of natural fungicides with that of chemical fungicides. In current investigation accession and comparison of the cytotoxic effect of the chemical fungicide 'carbendazim' and three natural fungicides, *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric) and *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemon grass) has been carried out. For the screening of the cytotoxic effect, *Allium cepa* is used due for dividing nature of root tip and large size of chromosome.

Plant based bioassay has been considered as simple, rapid and inexpensive tool in comparison to other standard methods (firebase and Anon 2014).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Clean and fresh onion bulbs were placed in glass jar containing test fungicides in different concentrations and for different time spans. Five concentrations of each fungicide were used. Carbendazim 0.1%,0.2%,0.3%,0.4% and 0.5% and *Azadirachta indica*, *Curcuma longa*, *Cymbopogon citratus* were taken in concentration series of 1%,2%, 3%, 4% and 5% respectively.

Root tips were collected from onion bulbs in each treatment for analysis of cytotoxic after 6, 12 and 24 hours of span. Tips were then fixed in Cornoy's fluid (3:1 ration of ethanol and glacial acetic acid), hydrolyzed (1N HCL) at 60° C for 5 min and washed with distilled water. Root tips were taken and stained with 2% acetocarmine and slides were prepared by

squash method. Cells were observed under 40X magnification under compound microscope. Observations were noted w.r.t. mitotic index and total aberration %. Cytotoxic parameters were calculated with the following formulae.

$$\text{Mitotic index} = \frac{\text{No. of dividing cells}}{\text{Total no. of cells}} \times 100$$

(Yakeen and Adeboye)

$$\text{Total abnormality \%} = \frac{\text{No. of abnormal cell}}{\text{Total no. of cells}} \times 100$$

Variance was taken trice and mean values were considered for conclusion.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In current study, aberrations are observed in root tip cells are Vagrant chromosomes in anaphase, anaphase bridge, binucleated cell, telophase bridge, and anaphase fragment.

Photo plate: Stages: A- normal prophase, B- normal metaphase, C- normal anaphase, D : normal telophase. E- metaphase with puff & breakage, F- anaphase-telophase with fragment, G&H- vagrant chromosomes in anaphase I- binucleated cell in prophase, J- strap nucleus

Table 1: Mitotic index and abnormalities observed in root apical meristem of *Allium cepa* treated with Carbendazim

Duration	Concentration (g/l)	% of mitotic index	% of aberration
6 hours	Control	54.9	0
	0.1%	51.4	3.77
	0.2%	37.64	7.65
	0.3%	29.31	14.56
	0.4%	20.03	22.91
	0.5%	18.07	26.32
12 hours	Control	60.6	0
	0.1%	44.19	7.8
	0.2%	28.97	11.11
	0.3%	26.24	15.68
	0.4%	19.22	24.76
	0.5%	17.39	27.08
24 Hours	Control	70.7	0
	0.1%	37.4	8.49
	0.2%	27.2	15.03
	0.3%	20.1	17.51
	0.4%	17.08	25.25
	0.5%	16.21	27.17

Table 2: Comparative Mitotic index and abnormalities observed in root apical meristem of *Allium cepa* treated with *Azadirachta indica*, *Curcuma longa*, *Cymbopogon citratus*

Duration	Concentration (g/l)	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>		<i>Curcuma longa</i>		<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	
		% of mitotic index	% of aberration	% of mitotic index	% of aberration	% of mitotic index	% of aberration
6 hours	Control	46.51	0	47.59	0	46.53	0
	1%	36.48	1.01	31.17	1.88	33.33	1.74
	2%	29.07	2.31	22.8	3.50	31.55	2.5
	3%	26.92	3.24	14.06	8.53	24.95	3.03
	4%	18.52	5.82	15.23	11.25	21.06	5.04
	5%	16.72	6.74	13.95	12.32	16.55	7.07
12 hours	Control	40.46	0	41.06	0	52.23	0
	1%	27.66	2.12	30.45	1.29	29.70	3.10
	2%	24.66	2.72	28.91	2.38	28.39	3.77
	3%	19.24	6.54	16.16	5.20	27.06	4.96
	4%	18.42	9.37	14.82	6.89	19.86	7.62
	5%	15.87	10.3	12.22	12.50	17.83	11.70
24 Hours	Control	41.54	0	50.49	0	40.19	0
	1%	23.18	3.18	27.77	2.75	36.27	2.64
	2%	24.27	4.92	26.03	3.78	29.74	4.60
	3%	19.61	8.03	18.35	7.33	28.54	5.96
	4%	18.03	10.10	13.66	8.86	24.47	7.91
	5%	15.46	12.74	12.26	12.50	16.36	13.18

In case of chemical fungicide, the treatment shows strong cytotoxic effect with time and dose. Highest cytotoxic effect is observed at 0.5% concentration at 24 hours. While across natural fungicide, Mitotic index is found to be decreasing with increasing concentration. Mitotic index also decreases with longer exposure of time. 5% concentration shows lowest mitotic index at all time spans, in all three plant-based fungicides. This indicates dose dependent and time dependent inhibitory effect on cell division.

Among all three natural fungicides, *Curcuma longa* showed greatest reduction in mitotic index and higher genotoxic effect, suggesting strong cytotoxic potential on onion root tip compared to other two natural fungicides

CONCLUSION

Compared to natural fungicides, chemical fungicide shows higher antimitotic and genotoxic properties with ten times less concentration. Therefore, natural fungicides should always be preferable over chemical fungicide. Among natural fungicides *Azadirachta indica* is least cytotoxic and genotoxic compared to *Curcuma longa* and *Cymbopogon citratus*.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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